

Chemical Investigations on *Knoxia corymbosa*

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Knoxia corymbosa (Fam. Rubiaceae), a small shrub in W. Bengal, on chemical studies, shows the presence of β -sitosterol and ursolic acid besides a considerable amount of oily residues.

Knoxia corymbosa, a small shrub belonging to Rubiaceae, is grown widely in Bengal plains. De Silva and Wijesckera¹ reported the presence of an "Unknown steroid, Knoxiol" and ursolic acid in the leaves of *K. zeylanica*, a Ceylonese plant having traditional reputation as an antidote for snakebite. Since no work on the Bengal plant, *K. corymbosa* was reported in literature, a chemical investigation of the whole plant was undertaken. The petroleum ether extract of the whole plant of *K. corymbosa* was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The neutral fraction on chromatography over activated alumina provided β -sitosterol, identified as its acetate by mixed melting point with an authentic sample, and the acidic fraction on chromatography of its methyl ester on activated alumina afforded ursolic acid as its methyl ester, identified as its acetate and methyl ester acetate with an authentic sample.

The ethanolic percolate of the defatted plant material did neither respond to any tests for alkaloid nor any crystalline solid material could be isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dried and powdered whole plants of *K. corymbosa* (750 gm) was extracted with light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet for 48 hrs and then percolated with 95% ethanol for one week. The greenish oily residue (3 gm) obtained on removal of solvent from light petrol extract was taken up in ether (300 ml) and washed with 5% aqueous KOH solution (3 × 50 ml).

The above ether layer was washed with cold water till neutral. The neutral ether soluble part (800 mg) was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina (60 gm). Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (1 : 1) furnished a solid (500 mg), m.p. 125–30° which (100 mg) was acetylated with acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (2 ml). The acetylated product (75 mg) on several crystallisations from methanol furnished β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 126–27° [α]_D³⁰ –35° (CHCl₃) (lit.² m.p. 127–28° [α]_D³⁰ –35° (CHCl₃) which was identical (mixed m.p.) an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate.

The above aqueous alkaline solution was acidified in cold when a flocculent precipitate was obtained which was taken up in ether (3 × 50 ml). The ether extract was washed with water and dried. The concentrated ether extract (30 ml) was treated with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (10 gm nitrosomethyl urea), kept overnight in cold and then worked up.

1. L. B. De Silva and R. O. B. Wijesckera, *J. Sci. Indus. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 508.

2. Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry, Edited by E. Jsephy and R. Radt, 1940, **14**, 90.

The methyl ester (2.50 gm) was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina (125 gm). Elution with benzene furnished a solid (1.75 gm), m.p. 140–45° which on several crystallisations from petroleum ether yielded fine glistening crystals of methyl ursolate, m.p. 166–67°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 58^\circ$ (CHCl₃) Lit.³ m.p. 165–67°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 58^\circ$, (Found C, 78.83; H, 10.59; Calc. for C₃₁H₅₀O₃ C, 79.15; H, 10.64%) which was identical (mixed m.p. and NMR characteristics) with an authentic specimen of methyl ursolate. Its identity was further confirmed through the preparations of ursolic acid, ursolic acid acetate and methyl ester acetate of ursolic acid.

Ursolic acid : Methyl ursolate (250 mg) was refluxed with 20% ethanolic potassium hydroxide (10 ml) for 6 hr. on a steam-bath, cooled, diluted with water (50 ml) and acidified with dil. HCl when a white mass was precipitated. It was taken into ether (3 × 50 ml), ether extract was washed with water, dried and concentrated. The residue obtained after concentration on repeated crystallisations from ethanol gave colourless needles (100 mg) of ursolic acid, m.p. 284–85°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 66^\circ$ (CHCl₃) (Lit.³ m.p. 291–2°). I.R.: 3520 cm⁻¹ (hydroxy), 1712 cm⁻¹ (acid carbonyl) and 1462 cm⁻¹ (carbon-methyl).

Ursolic acid acetate : 50 mg of the above acid was kept overnight with 5 ml. acetic anhydride and 2 ml. dry pyridine and then poured into crushed ice. The solid separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and chromatographed over a column of silica gel (50 gm). The benzene eluates on several crystallisations from petrol ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave ursolic acid acetate (30 mg), m.p. 288° (Lit.³ m.p. 286–88°) $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 73^\circ$.

Methyl ester acetate of Ursolic acid : 100 mg of methyl ursolate was kept overnight with 2 ml acetic anhydride and 1 ml pyridine. Worked up as before and chromatographed over silica gel. The solid obtained on crystallisations from petroleum ether gave shining crystals of methyl ester acetate of ursolic acid, m.p. 242–45°, (Lit.³ m.p. 246–7°).

The defatted plant material was percolated with 95% ethanol for seven days. The solvent was removed under low pressure and the residue was taken in chloroform (300 ml). The chloroform solution was washed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (1%, 3 × 50 ml). The aqueous acidic solution was worked up for the basic material when neither any solid could be isolated nor any tests for alkaloid could be obtained. The dry chloroform solution on removal of the solvent left a gummy residue (which gave no tests for alkaloid) from which no crystalline solid could be isolated.

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